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Palynostratigraphy, Age Determination and Depositional Environments of the Imo Shale Exposures at the Okigwe/Port Harcourt Express Road Junction Okigwe, Southeastern Nigeria

By

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The palynological study of the shale exposures at the Okigwe-Port Harcourt Express Road Junction Okigwe, Southeastern Nigeria yielded moderate records of palynomorphs dominated by palm pollen *Longapertites marginatus*, *L. vanendeenburi*, *Mauritidites crassiexinus*, *Spinizonocolpites echinatus*, *Echitriporites trianguliformis*, with abundant fern spores *Deltoidospora adriennis*, *Cyathidites minor*, common fungal spores and sparse records of the dinoflagellate cysts *Itecyta fusiforma*, *Itecyta heterospinosa*, *Phelodinium magnificum*, *P. africanum*, *Fibrocysta lappacea*, *Homotryblium tenuispinosum*, *Diphyes colligerum*, *Cerodinium* spp., *Ceratiopsis* spp., *Apectodinium* spp., *Kallosphaeridium* spp., *Cordosphaeridium* spp., *Exochosphaeridium* spp., *Spiniferites* spp., *Cleistosphaeridium* spp., and *Lejeunecysta* spp. The sequences composed of alternating successions of brown to grey, soft to moderately hard and fissile mudstones, with sand intercalations. Carbonaceous matter and ferruginous materials were the accessory minerals. The recovered micro floral assemblages with abundant plant debris, sparse cuticles, common fungal spores suggests near-shore to marginal marine depositional environments. Published ranges of the palynostratigraphically important taxa enabled the delineation of the age as Middle Paleocene – Early Eocene thereby indicating that the exposure belongs to the Imo Formation. Again, the preponderance of palm pollen supports the Cretaceous – Early Tertiary palm province which traversed the southern hemisphere. The kerogen analysis revealed that the samples were immature for oil and gas generation.

Keywords: Okigwe, Imo Formation, palynomorphs, kerogen, phytoclasts.

INTRODUCTION

The studied shale exposure is located at the Okigwe-Port Harcourt Express road junction in Okigwe southeastern Nigeria with bearings (Lat. 05° 49.201" N and Long. 007° 20.248 E), taken with a Garlux 70 GPS equipment. The sediments around Okigwe have been studied by workers such as (Obob *et al.* 2005; Umeji and Nwajide, 2007; Umeji and Edet, 2008) and dated accordingly as belonging to the Anambra Basin, one of the Nigerian Inland Basins. The oldest tertiary rock units recognized within this area have been assigned to the Late Maastrichtian – Middle Paleocene Nsukka Formation of the Anambra Basin (Fig. 1). The formation consists of a hard, shaley, glauconitic siltstone with thin beds of limestone and limestone concretions (Umeji and Nwajide, 2007). Again, Umeji and Edet (2008) had dated the Nsukka Formation Late Maastrichtian to Middle Paleocene and further dated the overlying Imo Formation as Paleocene. Obob *et al.* (2005) had dated the whole formation as Paleocene. Moreover, Short and Stäuble (1967) had reported that the age of the Nsukka Formation ranges between Maastrichtian to Paleocene, while the age of the overlying Imo Shale Formation ranges from Paleocene to Lower Eocene (Table 1). According to Avbovbo (1978) and Short and Stäuble (1967), the Imo Formation is the outcrop lithofacies equivalent of the Akata Formation in the subsurface Niger Delta. Oloto (1992) had studied core samples of the Late Paleocene- Early Eocene sections of the Imo Shale from the Gbekebo-1 well in the Benin Flank of the Niger Delta which yielded rich palynomorph assemblages. He recorded the dinoflagellate cysts *Achomosphaera ramulifera*, *Cordosphaeridium multispinosum*, *Adnatosphaeridium vittatum*, *Amiculosphaera umbracula*, *Apectodinium quinquelatum*, *Cannosphaeropsis utinensis*, *Ceratiopsis boloniensis*, *Cleistosphaeridium spinulastrum*, *Distatodinium virgatum*, *Emmetrocysta urnaformis*, *Fibrocyata vectense*, *Glaphyrocysta exuberans*, *G.ordinata*, *Hafniasphaera septata*, *Hystichokolpoma rigaudiae*, *Wetziella articulata*, *Impletosphaeridium cracens*, *I. ligospinosum*, *Muratodinium*

fimbriatum, *Operculodinium bellunum*, *Paleocystidium golzowense*, *Riculacacysta perforata* and various *Spiniferites* spp., which co-occurred with *Retidiporites magdalenensis*, *Foveotriletes margaritae* and *Proxapertites operculatus*. He reported that the Imo Shale represents a stratigraphic unit widely distributed over several hundreds of kilometres from the south east boundary of Nigeria across the Niger delta to the western boundary. He also confirmed a Late Paleocene to Early Eocene ages for the Imo Shale based on his findings from the Gbekebo-1 well. However, Oboh *et al.* (2005) had dated the Paleogene strata of the Anambra Basin/Afikpo Syncline from southeastern Nigeria they studied as Paleocene–Middle Eocene based on the recovered diagnostic palynomorphs such as *Longapertites vanendeenburghi*, *Proxapertites operculatus*, *Proxapertites cursus*, *Praedapollis africanus*, in association with the dinoflagellate cysts *Batiacasphaera* sp., *Spiniferites mirabilis*, foraminiferal wall linings, the Acritarch *Pterospermella* sp., freshwater algae *Pediastrum* spp., *Azolla* sp., and fungal elements. They inferred two depositional sequences within the Paleocene Imo Formation environments.

This project was undertaken to ascertain the age of the shale exposures at the Okigwe express road junction and infer whether it is of the same age as those reported by other workers around the Okigwe environment and also note whether there were variations in the depositional environments.

Figure 1: Geological Map of southern Nigeria showing the Anambra Basin and Imo Formation (Modified after Umeji and Edet 2008). Triangle shows study area.

Fig. 1: Geological Map of southern Nigeria showing the Anambra Basin and Imo Formation (Modified after Umeji and Edet 2008). Triangle shows study area.

Table 1: Table of Formations, Niger Delta Area

SUBSURFACE			SURFACE OUTCROPS		
Youngest		Oldest	Youngest		Oldest
Known Age		Known Age	Known Age		Known Age
Recent	Benin Formation (Afam Clay Member)	Oligocene	Plio/Pleistocene	Benin Formation	Miocene
Recent	Agbada Formation	Eocene	Miocene Eocene	Ogwashi-Asaba Formation Ameki Formation	Oligocene Eocene

Recent	Akata Formation	Eocene	L. Eocene	Imo Shale Formation	Paleocene
			Paleocene	Nsukka Formation	Maestrichtian
			Maestrichtian	Ajali Formation	Maestrichtian
			Campanian	Mamu Formation	Campanian
			Campanian/ Maestrichtian	Nkporo Shale	Santonian
			Coniacian/ Santonian	Awgu Shale	Turonian
EQUIVALENTS NOT KNOWN			Turonian	Eze Aku Shale	Turonian
			Albian	Asu River Group	Albian

Table 1 : Formatted after Short and Stauble (1967)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eleven outcrop samples were collected at 10cm intervals from the shale exposures (Figures 2) at the Okigwe/Port Harcourt Express road Junction Okigwe (Lat. 05° 49.201" N and Long. 007° 20.248 E) coordinates taken with Garlux 70 GPS on the 11th of June 2011. The samples were placed in sterile plastic bags, taken to the laboratory of the Department of Biological Sciences, Redeemers University where they were sorted and later prepared according to the method of Durugbo *et al.* (2010). The samples for palynofacies were not oxidized so as to retain the original colour of the palynomorphs and phytoclasts. The samples were analyzed and all the palynomorphs counted and recorded in analysis sheets to enhance the age dating and paleoenvironmental reconstruction. The analysis sheets were later entered in Microsoft EXCEL and the total occurrences and percentage occurrences of the different palynomorphs groups [palms, other pollen, spores, dinoflagellate cysts, microfaminiferal wall linings, acritarchs, freshwater algae and others (diatom frustules, fungal elements)] were calculated (Table 2). Photomicrographs of some of the common palynomorphs (Figs. 3-7) were taken with a Zeiss Axioskop 2 microscope with an attached Axiocam 1Cc 1 Camera at the Palynology laboratory of the Bernard Price Institute of Paleontological Research at the University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa. Furthermore, the palynofacies/kerogen slides were subjected to analysis under transmission light microscopy. The methods of Jaramillo and Oboh-Ikuenobe(1999) as modified by Udeze and Oboh-Ikuenobe(2005) was adopted where seven types of palynodebris viz: amorphous organic matter (AOM), black debris, degraded phytoclasts, structured phytoclasts (wood, parenchyma, cuticle), marine palynomorphs (dinoflagellate cysts, acritarchs, microfaminiferal wall linings), fungal remains (spores, hyphae, mycelia), and sporomorphs (spores and pollen) were identified. Three hundred particles (each with a 5 µm size cutoff) were point counted per slide and the data was later converted to percentages (Table 3). The unprocessed samples, slides, residues, CD copies and duplicate prints are housed in the palynological collections of the Biological Sciences Department, Redeemer's University, Mowe, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Fig. 2: The shale exposure at the Okigwe / Port Harcourt Express Road Junction, Okigwe. Arrow points at the thick shale overlain by thick boulders of rocks.

RESULTS

i) Palynology

The recovered palynomorphs were diverse and well preserved in all the samples. One hundred and thirteen palynomorphs with a total count of 1589 were recorded. Palm pollen made up of 10 genera and 19 species and a total count of 567 dominated the assemblages in all the samples, accounting for 35.68% of the total microfloral assemblage. These were followed successively by spores, with twelve species and total counts of 460, other pollen were 35 species with a total count of 184, fungal elements and diatom frustules altogether amounted to 125, dinoflagellate cysts composed of twenty eight genera and thirty nine species gave a total count of just 96, plus a total of 16 freshwater algae, with 14 acritarchs and one microforaminiferal wall linings (Table 2). The commonest palm pollen were *Longapertites marginatus*, *L. vanendeenburgi*, *Echitriporites trianguliformis*, *Spinizonocolpites echinatus* and *Retidiporites magdalenensis*. Generally, angiosperm pollen dominated as there were sparse records of gymnospermous pollen. This reveals the proliferation and diversification of the angiosperms in the Early Tertiary. The high counts of spores was influenced by the common records of *Deltoidospora adriennis* and *Cyathidites minor* with total counts of 219 and 205 respectively. The records of the organic walled microfossils revealed the dominance of gonyaulacoids over the peridinoids. Out of the thirty-nine dinoflagellate cysts recovered, 24 were gonyaulacoids, while fifteen were peridinoids. There appeared to be a cyclic trend in their occurrence with moderate counts of 6 and 18 in samples 1 and 2. Samples 3, 4 and 5 had counts of 2 dinoflagellates each, while none was recorded in sample 6, after which there was a gradual increase to 11 in sample 9, with a peak of 34 in sample 10 and 11 in sample 11.

Table 2: Total counts and percentage occurrence of the different palynomorph groups

Palynomorph Group	Total counts	Percentage
Total Palm pollen	567	35.68
Total Other pollen	310	19.51
Total Spores	460	28.95
Total Dinoflagellate cysts	96	6.04
Total Microforaminiferal wall linings	1	0.06
Total Acritarch	14	0.88
Total Freshwater algae	16	1.01
Total Others	125	7.87
Grand Total	1589	100

FIGURE 3

Figure 3: Photomicrographs of palynomorphs each identified by sample number and location coordinates. All figures X400. 1. *Echitriporites trianguliformis* Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964 Sample 2 (97.0/15.4); 2. *Psilatricolporites marginatus* Van Der Kaars 1983, Sample 8 (110.3/14.1); 3. *Longapertites marginatus* Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964 Sample 9 (106.2/13.6); 4. *Psilastephanocolporites cf. laevigatus* Sample 9 (106.2/13.6); 5. *Mauritidites crassibaculatus* Van. Hoeken-Klinkenberg 1964 Sample 9 (92.5.3/23.4); 6. *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis* Potonié & Gelletich 1933, Sample 4 (112.3/20.8); 7. *Leiotriletes adriennis* Potonié Gelletich Krutzch 1959 Sample 4 (105.5/10.6); 8. *Foveomonocolpites bauchiensis* Adegoke *et al.* 1978 Sample 2 (104.5/21.5); 9. *Psilamonocolpites medius* Jaramillo *et al.* 2007 Sample 4 (110.3/23.1); 10. *Diatom frustule* Sample 8 (95.1/11.6); 11. *Cyathidites minor* Couper, 1953, Kar 1990 Sample 8 (100.0/24.4); 12. *Leiotriletes adriennis* Potonié Gelletich Krutzch 1959 Sample 9 (110.10/7.2); 13. *Psilatirporites rotundus* Jan du Chene *et al.* (1978) Sample 9 (100.4/13.3); 14. *Longapertites marginatus* Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964 Sample 8 (95.3/11.5); 15. *Arecipites microreticulatus* Salami 1983 Sample 10 (98.7/21.10).

FIGURE 4

Figure 4: Photomicrographs of palynomorphs each identified by sample number and location coordinates. All figures X400.1. *Longapertites marginatus* Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964 Sample 4 (103.7/30.10); 2. *Longapertites vanendeenburgi* Sample 10 (99.5/15.1); 3. *Proxapertites operculatus* (Germeraad, Hopping and Muller, 1968) Sample 3 (104.8/23.8); 4. *Longapertites microfoveolatus* Adegoke *et al.* 1978 Sample 8 (116.6/5.3); 5. *Longapertites inornatus* Adegoke *et al.* 1978 Sample 4 (112.9/30.8); 6. *Longapertites vanendeenburgi* Sample 9 (105.8/20.10); 7. *Psilatricolporites saggitatus* Samant and Phadtare 1997 Sample 9 (94.2/15.6); 8. *Retidiporites magdalenensis* Van der Hammen and Garcia, 1966 Sample 4 (111.0/9.2); 9. *Margocolporites* sp. Sample 1 (118.8/15.4); 10. *Triorites* sp. Sample 8 (118.10/20.2); 11. *Arecipites* sp. Sample 10 (98.7/21.10); 12. *Psilatricolporites marginatus* Van Der Kaars 1983, Sample 9 (110.7/5.3); 13. *Psilatricolporites* sp. Sample 10 (105.6/10.6).

FIGURE 5

Figure 5: Photomicrographs of palynomorphs each identified by sample number and location coordinates. All figures X400. 1. *Spinizonocolpites echinatus* Muller, 1968 Sample 9(95.3/11.5); 2. *Triorites* sp. Sample 4 (105.4/15.10); 3. *Retitricolpites communis* Jaramillo *et al.* 2007 Sample 10 (96.3/18.2); 4. *cf. Psilatricolpites colpiconstrictus* Hoeken-Klinkenberg 1966 Sample 9 (94.2/15.6); 5. *Zlivisporis blanensis* Pacltova 1961 Sample 8 (102.8/12.7); 6. *Grimsdalea polygonalis* Jan du Chene *et al.* (1978) Sample 11 (116.6/5.3); 7. *Arecipites* sp. Sample 4 (103.7/30.10); 8. *Proxapertites operculatus* Germeraad, Hopping and Muller, 1968 Sample 4 (104.2/19.10); 9. *Brevicolporites guinetii* Salard-Cheboldaeff 1978 Sample 1(126.9/20.7); 10. *Ericipites pachyexinus* Salami 1985, Sample 9 (103.5/20.4); 11. *Longapertites marginatus* Van Hoeken-Klinkenberg, 1964 Sample 9(104.3/12.5); 12. *Perflotricolpites digitatus* Gonzàlez Guzmàn 1967 Sample 10 (98.9/20.7).

FIGURE 6

Figure 6: Photomicrographs of dinoflagellate cysts each identified by sample number and location coordinates. All figures X400, 1. *Cerodinium* sp. Sample 2 (94.5/25.6); 2. *Paleocystodinium* cf. *rafi* Oboh *et al.* 2007, Sample 9(102.5/21.2); 3. *Homotryblum abbreviatum* Eaton1976, Sample 2 (95.0/10.1); 4. *Spiniferites mirabilis* Rossignol 1963, Sample 9 (94.4/7.4); 5. *Phelodinium africanum* Biffi and Grignani, 1983, Sample 3 (116.4/18.2); 6. *Apectodinium* cf. *quiquelatum* (Williams & Downie, 1966) Costa & Downie, 1979, Sample 9(109.9/22.9); 7. *Spiniferites pachyderma* Sample 10(102.10/20.4); 8. *Hystrichokolpoma rigaudiae* Deflandre & Cookson 1955 Sample 5(99.1/20.10); 9. ? *Ceratiopsis* sp. Sample 9 (94.5/25.6); 10. *Homotryblum tenuispinosum* Davey and Williams 1966 Sample 2 (95.5/24.8); 11. *Kallosphaeridium* cf. *yorubaense* Jan Du Chene and Adediran 1985, Sample 7(107.5/25.8); 12. *Selenopemphix* cf. *nephroides* Sample 3 (99.8/28.7).

FIGURE 7

Figure 7: Photomicrographs of dinoflagellate cysts each identified by sample number and location coordinates. All figures X400, 1. *Fibrocysta lappacea* (Drugg, 1970) Stover and Evitt, 1978 Sample 3 (120.9/18.5); 2. *Impagidinium* sp. Sample 9 (106.5/5.0); 3. *Paleoperidinium pyrophorum* Willumsen (2002, 2003) Sample 10 (104.6/12.4); 4. *Lejeunecysta lata* Biffi and Grignani, 1983, Sample 2 (112.5/14.3); 5. *Ifecysta heterospinosa* Jan du Chêne and Adediran, 1985, Sample 3 (116.4/18.2); 6. *Lingulodinium machaerophorum* (Deflandre and Cookson 1955) Wall, 1967 Sample 7 (104.5/12.4); 7. *Spiniferites pachyderma* Rossignol 1964 Sample 9 (102.5/21.2); 8. Peridinoid Sample 1 (117.10/29.10); 9. *Operculodinium israelianum* Rossignol (1962) Wall 1967 Sample 10 (102.5/10.8); 10. *Operculodinium centrocarpum* (Deflandre and Cookson) Wall, 1967 Sample 10 (103.8/22.8); 11. *Phelodinium magnificum* (Stanley, 1965) Stover and Evitt, 1978, Sample 10 (91.6/24.5); 12. *Cordosphaeridium exilimurum* Davey and Williams, 1966 Sample 3 (102.5/21.2).

ii) Palynofacies

Jaramillo and Oboh-Ikuenobe (1999) had categorized common palynodebris into terrestrial structureless (resins, black debris, yellow-brown fragments and black-brown fragments) and terrestrial structured (cuticles, plant tissue, woody material, pollen and spores and fungi), while the marine components are made up of (aquatic structureless organic matter, aquatic structured, (dinoflagellate cysts and foraminiferal wall linings). In the studied sample, the palynofacies (Table 3) varied from samples with mostly unstructured and degraded phytoclasts (samples 2, 7 and 11), moderate percentages of structured phytoclasts (Samples 3-8), with common pollen and spores and rare structureless organic matter except in samples 2, 9, 10, 11, in which marine indices were moderate (Figure 8). This indicates nearshore depositional environments since structure less organic matter (AOM) and lath shaped woody materials normally associated with more marine environments were not so abundant (Oboh-Ikuenobe *et al.* 2005). Again, though the dinoflagellate cysts suite was dominated by gonyaulacoids (24 species) as against 15 species of peridinoids, most of them were low salinity indicators (Edet and Nyong, 1993).

Table 3: Total counts of the different palynofacies groups by samples

Sample	Sporomorphs	Fungal Remains	Marine palynomorphs	Amorphous organic matter	Structured phytoclasts	Unstructured /degraded phytoclasts	Black debris	Total
1	12	26	16	10	128	89	19	300
2	8	14	20	16	86	128	28	300
3	5	10	6	7	148	88	36	300
4	7	15	5	8	135	98	32	300
5	5	10	6	10	148	92	29	300
6	6	9	2	12	153	80	38	300
7	5	10	13	12	130	98	32	300
8	7	12	4	8	150	79	40	300
9	26	15	16	18	92	55	78	300
10	20	10	18	38	48	96	70	300
11	12	17	14	46	65	100	46	300

Figure 8: Sample by sample Percentage plot of the recovered phytoclasts

i) Kerogen analysis

Using *Deltoidospora adriennis* which was common in all the studied samples, its golden yellow colour suggests that the sediments were immature for oil and gas generation as the colour correlates with an SCI (Spore colour Index) of 4.0-4.5 (Matchette-Downes, 2009).

DISCUSSION

The recovery of abundant palm pollen *Longapertites marginatus*, *Longapertites vanendeenburgi*, *Retidiporites magdalenensis*, *Echitriporites trianguliformis*, *Spinizonocolpites echinatus*, *Spinizonocolpites baculatus*, *Proxapertites operculatus*, *Proxapertites cursus*, concurs with the Cretaceous – Early Tertiary palm province of (Herngreen, 1980; Herngreen *et al.* 1996; Herngreen and Chlonova, 1981; Morley, 2000; Atta-Peters and Salami 2004; Jaramillo *et al.*, 2007). This province traversed the whole of the southern hemisphere just as Eisawi and Shrank (2008), Jaramillo *et al.*, (2007) and Kaska (1989) had all reported. Again from the offshore Tano Basin in Ghana, Atta-Peters and Salami (2004) recovered similar palynomorphs such as *Longapertites vanendeenburgi*, *L. marginatus*, *L. proxapertitoides*, *Spinizonocolpites baculatus*, *S. echinatus*, *Proxapertites cursus*, *P. operculatus*, *Echitriporites trianguliformis*, *Mauritidites crassibaculatus*, *Zlavisporis blanensis*, together with *Foveotriletes margaritae*, *Proteacidites dehaani*, *Cingulatisporiites ornatus*, *Buttinea andreevi*, *Auriculiidites reticulatus*, which were of older ages and such younger forms as *Retistephanocolpites williamsi*, *Pachydermites diederixi*, *Verrucatosporites usmensis*, *Praedapollis africanus* for the samples they studied ranged from Campanian to Eocene. The absence of the latter in the Okigwe samples supports the inferred Late Paleocene to Early Eocene age. Furthermore, Eisawi and Shrank (2008) had also associated *L. marginatus*, *Foveomonocolpites bauchiensis*, *Racemonocolpites facilis*, *Monocolpites marginatus*, *Syncolporites marginatus* with the Paleocene and *Proxapertites operculatus*, *Cicatricosisporites dorogensis*, *Spinizonocolpites echinatus*, *Mauritiidites crassiexinus*, *Echitriporites trianguliformis*, *Retistephanocolpites williamsi*, and *Bacutriporites orluensis* with the Eocene of the Melut Basin in Sudan. Again, Salami (1983) in studying the Upper Senonian (Maastrichtian) and Lower Tertiary (Paleocene-Eocene) pollen grains from southern Nigeria had recorded *Longapertites vanendeenburgi*, *L. marginatus*, *Retidiporites magdalenensis*, *Retistephanocolpites williamsi*, *Arecipites microreticulatus*, *Ericipites pachyexinus*, *Bacutriporites orluensis*, *E. trianguliformis* among the younger palynomorphs which co-occurred with *Proteacidites dehaani*, *Constructipollenites ineffectus*, *Nigeripollis gemmatus*, *Auriculiidites reticulatus* and *Mauritidites crassibaculatus* which were among the recovered palynomorphs from the Okigwe samples.

Adegoke *et al.* (1978) had used the presence of *Longapertites inornatus*, *L. marginatus*, *L. microfoveolatus*, *Foveomonocolpites bauchiensis*, *Monocolpites marginatus*, *Mauritidites crassibaculatus*, *P. operculatus*, *Retimonocolpites noremi*, *Cranwellipollis gombeensis* and *Bacutricolpites portiskumensis* to assign a Paleocene age to the Kerri-Kerri Formation in Northern Nigeria. Furthermore, Salard (1979) had listed *Psilamonocolpites medius*, *P. cursus*, *Triorites tenuiexinus*, *Syncolporites marginatus*, *Monocolpites* spp., under the Late Paleocene *Proxapertites operculatus* zone, while the basal Eocene assemblage is composed of *Retibrevitricolpites triangulatus*, *Triorites festatus*, *P. operculatus*, *Grimsdalea polygonalis*, *Arecipites* spp., *Monoporites annulatus* among others of which majority were present especially at the younger sections of the Okigwe samples.

Bankole *et al.* (2006) and Ojo and Akande (2006) had both inferred the palm province for the Late Paleocene to Early Eocene Oshosun Formation of the Dahomey Basin and the Upper Cretaceous Patti Formation of Southern Bida Basin, Nigeria respectively. The abundance of *Longapertites* spp., over *Proxapertites* spp. in these Okigwe express samples strongly supports the penetration of Paleocene sediments and the recovery of the dinoflagellate cyst *Homotryblium tenuispinosum* in sample 1, indicated the penetration of Middle Paleocene (Wall *et al.*, 1977). Furthermore, the Early Eocene is supported by the presence of *Grimsdalea polygonalis* and *Retibrevitricolpites triangulatus* especially in the uppermost sample (sample 11). Jan du Chene *et al.*, (1978) had recovered *G. polygonalis* along with other palynomorphs from the Eocene Ogwashi-Asaba Formation of Southeastern Nigeria while Salard-Cheboldaef (1979) had listed it among Early Eocene palynomorphs. Again, Eisawi and Shrank (2008) had also associated *M. crassiexinus* with the Eocene of Sudan as mentioned earlier.

The Okigwe express samples also resembled the A and B assemblages of Vadja-Santivaney (1999) from Bolivia and Atta-Peters and Salami (2004) assemblage from the Tano Basin, Ghana in which angiosperm pollen dominated pteridophyte spores and gymnospermous pollen. The common records of spores and palms as highlighted above gives credence to a dominantly wet climate.

Bankole *et al.* (2006) had recovered the dinoflagellate cysts *Ifecysta pachyderma*, *Apectodinium homomorphum*, *A. quinquelatum*, *A. paniculatum*., *Kallosphaeridium cf. brevibarbatum*, *Hafniasphaera septata*, which they had designated as age diagnostic species of the Late Paleocene (Thanetian) to Early Eocene (Ypresian) Oshosun Formation in the Nigerian Dahomey Basin. Edwards (1991) had also reported the occurrence of *Ifecysta*

pachyderma, *Hafniasphaera septata*, from her study of Paleocene and Eocene sediments from the Salt Range, Punjab, Pakistan. Furthermore, Quattrocchio (2009) had assigned a Late Danian to Late Selandian age to the Chorrillo Chico Formation at Punta Prat in Southern Chile based on the presence of *Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum* which was also recovered in the Okigwe samples. Jan du Chene and Adeniran (1985) had recovered *Ifeycta pachyderma*, *Fibrocysta lappacea*, *Phelodinium magnificum*, *Apectodinium homomorphum*, *H. paniculatum*, *H. hyperacanthum*, *H. quinquelatum*, *H. summissum*, *Cordosphaeridium exilimurum*, *C. multispinosum*, *Lentinia orei*, (*Lejeunecysta* spp.), *Adnatosphaeridium membraniphorum*, *A. multispinosum*, *Achomosphaera alcornu*, *Eocladopyxis paniculata*, *Diphyes spinulum*, *Kallosphaeridium orchiesense*, *K. yorubaensis*, *Muratodinium fimbriatum*, *Hystrichokolpoma rigaudiae*, *H. granulum*, *H. fenestratum*, *Homotryblium abbreviatum*, *Heteraulacysta granulata*, *H. pustulata*, *Spiniferites* spp., *Polysphaeridium zoharyi*, *Wetzeliella africaensis*, *Wilsodinium nigerians*, *Paleocystodinium golzowense*, *Deflandrea wardenensis* and *Tithyrodinium evittii*, from Late Paleocene – Early Eocene outcrops of the Imo shale along the Benin-Ore Highway.

Jan du Chene (1987) had reported the occurrence of *Phelodinium magnificum* and *P. africanum* from the Danian of Senegal. Biffi and Grignani (1983) had also recovered *Phelodinium magnificum*, *P. africanum* together with varied species of *Lejeunecysta* and *Selenopemphix* from the Niger Delta Oligocene sediments. Furthermore, Bankole *et al.* (2006) had recovered *L. beninensis*, *L. cinctoria*, *L. communis* and *L. lata* from the Late Paleocene to Early Eocene Oshosun Formation. Their presence in the Okigwe express samples suggests that *Phelodinium* spp. possibly evolved during the Early Paleocene and thrived till the Early Eocene. On the other hand, *Lejeunecysta* and *Selenopemphix* spp., may have also evolved during the Paleocene and had their acme during the Oligocene in the Nigerian Niger Delta.

Furthermore, Quattrocchio (2009) in studying Paleogene dinoflagellate cysts from the Chorrillo Chico and Agua Fresca Formations at Punta Prat, Southern Chile had also recovered such species as *Lejeunecysta fallax*, *Palaeocystodinium golzowense*, *Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum*, *Spiniferites membranaceus*, *S. ramosus*, *Phelodinium* sp., *Areoligera* sp., *Cerodinium* sp., which were also encountered in the Okigwe samples. However, he reported that Quattrocchio and Sargeant (2003) had earlier recovered twenty seven dinoflagellate cysts from the Chorrillo Chico Formation at Punta Prat among which were *Cassidium fragile*, *Deflandrea cygniformis*, *Deflandrea fuegensis*, *Eisenackia crassitabulata*, *Glaphyrocysta retiintexta*, *Isabelidinium bakeri*, *Impagidinium crassiculum*, *Palaeocystodinium golzowense*, *Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum*, *Pyxidiniopsis crassimurata*, *Spiniferella cornuta*, *Spiniferites (Hafniasphaera) cryptovesiculata* and *Turbiosphaera filosa*, some of these also show some affinity with the Okigwe samples. The presence of the diagnostic Late Paleocene (Thanetian) – Early Eocene dinoflagellate cysts *Apectodinium* spp. (Guasti *et al.* 2006), together with *Homotryblium tenuispinosum* and relics of the species of *Ifeycta*, *Fibrocysta*, *Cerodinium*, *Cordosphaeridium*, *Kallosphaeridium* and *Phelodinium* all support the Middle Paleocene-Early Eocene age.

The preponderance of palm pollen co-occurring with moderate recoveries of organic walled microfossils especially in samples 1, 2, 9, 10,11 suggests environments that fluctuated between near shore to marginal marine. Bruno *et al.* (2011) had used the percentage occurrences of dinoflagellate cysts in combination with spores and pollen to infer dominantly marine settings, where the former dominated and shallow marine environments in situations where the dinoflagellate cysts occurred with appreciable amounts of spores and pollen respectively. The dominance of the dinoflagellate suite by gonyaulacoids co-occurring with peridinoids supported this inference. Edet and Nyong (1993) had also posited that organic walled microfossils such as dinoflagellate cysts are more common in sediments deposited in marine conditions as against terrestrial components such as pollen and spores. They used statistical data of organic walled microfossils and miospores to distinguish between marine and non-marine environments. Reijers *et al.* (1997) had earlier reported that the Imo Formation is composed of shallow marine shelf sediments. Again, Stevens *et al.* (2011) had also inferred a coastal and shallow marine depositional environment for the Imo Formation around Bende in Southeastern Nigeria based on recovered ichthyofauna. The nearshore environment is further supported by the presence of dominant palms, spores, land derived phytoclasts, common fungal elements, freshwater algae and rare structureless organic matter. High influx of terrestrial materials causing dilution could have led to the low counts of dinoflagellate cysts.

Conclusively, the studied sediments from the Okigwe express junction are immature for oil and gas generation.

Table 4: Stratigraphic Ranges of Some Key Taxa

LATE CRETACEOUS			EARLY TERTIARY				AGE
CAMPANIAN	MAASTRICHTIAN		PALEOCENE			EOCENE	PALYNOMORPH TAXA
	E	M	E	M	L		
							<i>Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum</i>
							<i>Phelodinium magnificum</i>
							<i>Apectodinium homomorphum</i>
							<i>Apectodinium quinquelatum</i>
							<i>Proteacidites dehaani</i>
							<i>Spinizonocolpites echinatus</i>
							<i>Periretisyncolpites magnosagenatus</i>
							<i>Longapertites microfoveolatus</i>
							<i>Echitriporites trianguliformis</i>
						-----	<i>Longapertites marginatus</i>
							<i>Echiperiporites icacinoides</i>
							<i>Proxapertites operculatus</i>

Composite stratigraphical ranges of some selected species of palynomorphs from the Okigwe express (Adapted from various Authors)

CONCLUSION

This study has shed more light on the palynology of the Imo Formation thereby confirming the age as Late Paleocene – Early Eocene. The palynoflora revealed an assemblage similar to the palm province of (Herngreen and Chlonova, 1981; Herngreen *et al.* 1996 and Jaramillo *et al.* 2007). The environment of deposition are inferred to be predominantly shallow marine (Near shore) to marginal marine because of the preponderance of palm, other associated pollen, abundant phytoclasts and dominantly gonyaulacoid dinocysts. The climate must have fluctuated between warm/humid to cold and humid due to the presence of the warm water dinoflagellate cysts *Apectodinium* spp., and *Homotryblum* spp. co-occurring with moderate records of spores and palms.

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APPENDIX 1: DISTRIBUTION OF THE RECOVERED PALYNOMORPHS PER SAMPLE

OKIGWE EXPRESS PALYNOMORPH DISTRIBUTION DATA

S/NO	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	Sample 7	Sample 8	Sample 9	Sample 10	Sample 11	Total	
TAXON													
Pollen (Palms)													
1	<i>Arecipites microreticulatus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	
2	<i>Echitriporites trianguliformis</i>	8	9	0	0	0	2	1	7	8	17	3	55
3	<i>Foveomonocolpites bauchiensis</i>	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0		3	7
4	<i>Longapertites marginatus</i>	58	35	9	30	9	7	9	9	20	29	51	266
5	<i>Longapertites microfoveolatus</i>	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
6	<i>Longapertites vanendeenburgi</i>	20	15	4	5	0	1	0	5	5	10	17	82
7	<i>Longapertites inornatus</i>	1	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	4	10
8	<i>Mauritidites crassibaculatus</i>	5	0	1	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	4	15
9	<i>Mauritidites crassixinus</i>	2	2	2	1	0	2	0	1	2	0	2	14
10	<i>Monocolpites spp.</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	3
11	<i>Monocolpites marginatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	8	14
12	<i>Proxapertites sulcatus</i>	0	4	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
13	<i>Psilamonocolpites medius</i>	3	0	0	2	0	1	0	4	5	0	0	15
14	<i>Retidiporites magdalenensis</i>	4	3	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	8	21
15	<i>Retimonocolpites bauchiensis</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
16	<i>Retimonocolpites nigeriensis</i>	9	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10

17	<i>Retimonocolpites noremi</i>	0	4	2	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	11
18	<i>Spinizonocolpites baculatus</i>	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	5
19	<i>Spinizonocolpites echinatus</i>	7	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	10	25
	Total	124	83	18	49	11	17	11	32	47	65	110	567
	Other Pollen												
1	<i>Bacutripites orluensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
2	<i>Bombacidites polanuris</i>	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
3	<i>Brevicolporites guineeti</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	4
4	<i>Chenopodipollis</i> spp.	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
5	<i>Corsinipollenites jussiaensis</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
6	<i>Crototricolporites fragilis</i>	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
7	<i>Echiperipites icacinoides</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	13	16
8	<i>Ephedripites multicostatus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
9	<i>Ephedripites</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
10	<i>Ericipites pachyexinus</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	4
11	<i>Grimsdalea polygonalis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3
12	<i>Ilexpollenites</i> spp.	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
13	<i>Margocolporites</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
14	<i>Monoporites annulatus</i>	12	3	1	3	2	0	1		1		1	24
15	<i>Perflotricolpites digitatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
16	<i>Periretisyncolpites magnosagentus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	4
17	<i>Proteacidites dehaani</i>	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	6
18	<i>Proteacidites miniporatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	3
19	<i>Proxapertites cursus</i>	17	14	3	10	2	5	3	8	3	7	18	90
20	<i>Proxapertites operculatus</i>	6	10	2	3	1	0	1	0	4	5	4	36
21	<i>Psilatricolporites marginatus</i>	2	0	1	1	1	2	2	3	0	0	0	12
22	<i>Psilatricolporites crassus</i>	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	5	14
23	<i>Psilatricolporites</i> spp.	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	10
24	<i>Psilastephanocolporites laevigatus</i>	3	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	6
25	<i>Retibrevitricolporites triangulatus</i>	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	4
26	<i>Retitricolpites crassicosatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
27	<i>Retitricolporites</i> spp.	4	3	0	1	1	2	0	2	0	5	7	25
28	<i>Retitricolpites communis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
29	<i>Rhoipites</i> spp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	5	7
30	<i>Striatopollis</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
31	<i>Syncolporites marginatus</i>	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
32	<i>Syncolporites lisame</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
33	<i>Syncolporites</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
34	<i>Syndemicolpites typicus</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
35	<i>Tricolpites</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	3
36	<i>Triorites</i> spp.	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	5
37	Indeterminate pollen	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
	Total												310

Spores

1	<i>Cicatricosisporites dorogensis</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	<i>Cyathidites minor</i>	15	4	2	11	4	3	11	4	14	50	87	205
3	<i>Cyathidites australis</i>	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	6
4	<i>Leotriletes adriennis</i>	30	30	10	5	7	4	4	6	5	51	67	219
5	<i>Echitriletes</i> spp.	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
6	<i>Foveotriletes margaritae</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
7	<i>Laevigatosporites</i> spp.	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	4	6	14
8	<i>Retitriletes</i> spp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
9	<i>Verrucatosporites</i> spp.	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	7
10	<i>Polypodiaceoisporites</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
11	<i>?Zlivisporis blanensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
12	Indeterminate spore	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
	Total	53	36	13	21	11	7	15	11	21	109	163	460

Dinoflagellate cysts

1	<i>Achomosphaera</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
2	<i>Apectodinium cf. homomorphum</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
3	<i>Apectodinium cf. quinquelatum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
4	<i>Areoligera</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	1	5
5	<i>Batiacasphaera</i> spp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	6
6	<i>?Ceratiopsis</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
7	<i>Cerodinium granulostriatum</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
8	<i>Cleistosphaeridium</i> spp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	5
9	<i>Cordosphaeridium</i> spp.	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	3
10	<i>Diphyes colligerum</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
11	<i>Exochosphaeridium</i> spp.	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	5
12	<i>Fibrocysta lapaccea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
13	<i>Glaphyrocysta</i> spp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
14	<i>Hafniasphaera septata</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	4
15	<i>Homotryblium tenuispinosum</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
16	<i>Homotryblium vallum</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
17	<i>Hystrichokolpoma rigaudiae</i>	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
18	<i>Ifecysta heterospina</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
19	<i>Ifecysta fusiforma</i>	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
20	<i>Impagidinium celinea</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
21	<i>Kallosphaeridium cf. yorubaense</i>	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	7
22	<i>Kallosphaeridium cf. capulatum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
23	<i>Lejeunecysta communis</i>	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
24	<i>Lejeunecysta fallax</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
25	<i>Lejeunecysta globosa</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
26	<i>Lejeunecysta lata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
27	<i>Lingulodinium machaerophirum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
28	<i>Oligosphaeridium cf. complex</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

29	<i>Operculodinium centrocarpum</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	4
30	<i>Palaeoperidinium pyrophorum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
31	<i>Paleocystodinium australinum</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2
32	<i>Phelodinium magnificum</i>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3
33	<i>Phelodinium africanum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
34	<i>Polysphaeridium subtile</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
35	<i>Polysphaeridium zoharyi</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
36	<i>Selenopemphix cf nephroides</i>	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
37	<i>Spiniferites perforatus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
38	<i>Spiniferites membranaceus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
39	<i>Spiniferites ramosus</i>	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	1	6
40	Indeterminate dinocysts	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	1	6
	Total	6	18	2	2	2	0	8	2	11	34	11	96
1	Foraminiferal wall lining	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Acritarchs												
1	<i>Leiosphaeridia</i> spp.	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	4	3	13
2	<i>Acritarch</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
													14
	Algae												
	<i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	5	6	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	16
	Others												
1	Fungal spores/hypha	44	9	4	7	3	1	3	4	1	8	15	99
2	Diatom Frustules	20	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	26
													125